

ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION UNIT

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Annotation: The development of environmental education and training in the Republic of Uzbekistan reflected in the nature of the work carried out in the field.

The environmental interpretation of the existence of some problems in the implementation of discipline.

"The characteristic feature of the nature intermingle to show these people the" summary of the round table, organized by topic.

Key words: environmental education and training, environmental issues, environmental education, ecological literacy, healthy lifestyle

From the day when the Republic of Uzbekistan gained its independence, the attention to the development of the plan for the future work, to ensure the correct assessment of the environment, to ensure the timely implementation of the necessary measures 1- He was in the center of attention of the president. After all, the 1st year Mother Nature, treating her with love, and enjoying her beauty are of great importance in the rise of human spirituality, the head of state said: "Closeness to nature, enjoying the carefree beauty of our beloved country nourishes and strengthens spirituality." they were right when they said that. The feeling of loving Mother Nature, enjoying her beauty, depends on the education given to the young generation. First of all, it is necessary to equip future teachers with environmental knowledge. In this regard hthat the modern generation observes local and spiritual ecological crisis situations, that the scientific-theoretical, practical, educational, cultural and informational importance of ecology is increasing in such a complicated period, the correct assessment of the environment, the necessary measures to ensure that it is carried out on time. it is important to conduct monitoring with diagnosis of

the level of development of ecological knowledge. Because environmental education is the focus of the UN, UNESCO and UNEP. To develop environmental education and upbringing, various events are being held on the scale of the world and individual countries. Every field specialist should be ecologically literate and should not harm nature in his activities, should contribute to the development of ecological education. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the field of development of environmental education and upbringing, appropriate activities are being organized and certain activities are being held. A continuous concept of environmental education has been developed in our country. But there are still many shortcomings in this regard. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Nature Protection" has given little place to this issue. The ecological information system is not well formed. These problems will be solved positively in the coming years. There is no doubt that the 21st century will be the century of ecology. Everyone should change our mother planet without harming nature, use natural resources wisely and contribute to the sacred task of preserving the living environment.

The formation of a healthy lifestyle cannot be imagined without a clean environment, in other words, without an ecologically safe natural environment. A healthy lifestyle and the environment are closely related. Healthy environment, cleanliness and purity of natural environment is one of the main factors of children's healthy and mature adulthood.

Environmental problems arise due to the lack of environmental education, its improper implementation, or some deficiencies in its organization. Environmental problems affect development, security, people's lives, and directly affect people's life expectancy, especially the lives of children, who are the youngest part of the population. It's no secret that the polluted, poisoned environment has a great impact on the still young, developing organism, and can't help but affect its physiological and mental development. Solving the problems of studying, explaining and evaluating the state of the environment, the introduction of the concepts of ecological forecasting and ecological expertise into consumption created the need

for the development of ecological knowledge. This is a necessity for environmental protection in Uzbekistan. made the issues of education and its development relevant. This relevance is aimed at providing environmental education not only in natural sciences such as ecology, biology, chemistry, but also in all types of sciences, including the Russian language, which is part of social science. In fact, environmental education plays an important role in protecting nature, rational use of nature and improvement of ecological conditions. The ecological situation in different countries, the characteristics of nature use largely depend on the level of ecological literacy of the population and ecological culture. Environmental education begins with the family. Environmental education should continue continuously from kindergarten to higher educational institutions. It is the main task of us teachers to educate love for nature from a young age. A highly experienced teacher develops an ecological education program and technology for its implementation, taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students. Through a roundtable discussion organized on the topic of "showing is a characteristic of people", it was determined how little they have ecological knowledge. In this regard, we used test and brainstorming questions. Sample of tests used: According to the conducted experiments, it was determined that they have insufficient ecological knowledge through a round discussion organized with the students of the 1st stage of the pedagogical institute on the topic "Showing kindness to nature is a characteristic of people". In this regard, we used test and brainstorming questions. Sample of tests used: According to the conducted experiments, it was determined that they have insufficient ecological knowledge through a round discussion organized with the students of the 1st stage of the pedagogical institute on the topic "Showing kindness to nature is a characteristic of people". In this regard, we used test and brainstorming questions. Sample of tests used:

<p>1. How many plant species are there on our planet? a*) more than 500 thousand b) more than 300 thousand c) more than 200 thousand d) more than 700 thousand.</p>	<p>3. When was the international "red book" established? a*) 1966 b) 1976 c) 1776 d) 1834</p>
<p>4. How many species of vertebrates are there in Uzbekistan? a) 582 ta b*) 682 ta c) 782 ta d) 884</p>	<p>4. Which century will undoubtedly be the ecological century? a) XII century b) XXV century c*) XXI century d) XVIII century</p>

The answers to the tests were asked individually, each answer was enriched with independent opinions. The students' knowledge was evaluated in general. Then, in order to find out the mutual opinions of 2 people, "Brainstorming" was started and the following questions were used:

- What are the reasons for the need to develop environmental knowledge?
- What forms of environmental education do you know?
- What do you mean by ecological culture?
- What are the organizations that focus on environmental education?
- What activities have been carried out in the field of environmental education development in the Republic of Uzbekistan?
- What is the role of plants in human and animal life?
- What can be achieved by teaching children to be environmentally friendly?
- Why do we need environmental education?

It was recommended to generate ideas before answering the questions. Then the most advanced ideas were selected.

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